

TAJIK-TURKISH LITERARY RELATIONS

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Аннотация. Благодаря деятельности таджикских переводчиков читатели получили возможность прочитать на родном языке некоторые произведения турецкой литературы. Представленный нами обзор не только позволяет воссоздать в наиболее полном виде хронологию переводческой деятельности произведений турецкой литературы в Таджикистане, но и отдать дань уважения истинным сподвижникам переводческого и издательского дела, внесшим неоценимый вклад в культуру таджикского общества.

Ключевые слова: труды, исследования, история, литература, развитие, интеллектуалы, издательское дело, переводчик, язык, книга, посредник.

Abstract. Thus, thanks to Tajik translator's activities public readers had the opportunity to read in their native language some works of Turkish literature. We presented an overview not only allows you to recreate in the most complete form of transfer activity chronology works of Turkish literature in Tajikistan, but also pay tribute to the true devotees translating and publishing, have made an invaluable contribution to the culture of Tajik society.

Keywords: works, studies, history, literature, development, intellectuals, Publishing, translator, language, the book, the mediator.

Annotatsiya. Tojik tarjimonlarining mehnati tufayli kitobxonlar turkiy adabiyotning ayrim asarlarini ona tilida o'qish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ldilar. Biz taqdim etgan taqriz nafaqat Tojikistondagi turk adabiyoti asarlarining tarjima faoliyati xronologiyasini to'liq shaklda qayta yaratishga, balki tarjima va nashriyotning haqiqiy fidoyilariga hurmat bajo keltirish imkonini beradi. tojik jamiyati madaniyati.

Kalit so'zlar: asarlar, tadqiqot, tarix, adabiyot, taraqqiyot, ziyolilar, nashriyot, tarjimon, til, kitob, vositachi.

The main means of perception of foreign literature in any national environment is literary translation. Therefore, the history of perception - first of all, the history of literary translation is devoted to this fact. History of translations of Turkish literary and artistic works in Tajikistan from the second half of the twentieth century to the present day. The interest of Tajik translators in Turkish literature in the 50s of the twentieth century will appear on the wave of increased interest in the works of Western literature. The first translation of a Turkish work of art was the story «Baby Hasan» by Ali Sabakhedtin, made from Russian into Tajik. The stories were enthusiastically accepted by the Tajik reader, which was largely due to the idea of the struggle of the new with the old, which corresponded to the then spiritual mood of Turkish society. After a three-year break, translations of Turkish poetic works began to appear more and more often on the pages of metropolitan and provincial newspapers. However, due to the different nature of the titles of some poems, their authorship, and also the fact that translations were made from Russian.

In 1954, the first poetic translation into Tajik was published by the «Poems» of the Turkish poet, writer, screenwriter, playwright and public figure Nazim Hikmet. Later, the translation of the novel «Romance» (translated by K. Nosirov, was published in 1966 by the publishing house «Irfon»), and the stories: «Memory of N. Hikmet» (translated by A. Nasimov, Education and Culture, 01/22/1972), «Mirror of the Heart» (translated by A. Vositzade, 1979, «Education and

Culture)), «Song of the Free Island» (translated from Russian by S. Sultan, «Komsomolsk Tajikistan», 01/05/1975), as well as short stories: «I Want to Warm Up», «Let My Son Become a Sailor», «Umbrella and Cane», «Death of a Duckling», «Pregnancy», «Reading», «Man and Nature» (translated by A. Nasimov, «Education and Culture» 1.05.1975), «The Cloud in Love» (stories for young people), translated from the original by R. Hashim, «Irfon» 1972. 92 pages). This book also offers the author's preface to the Russian translation: «The Story of Three Babies», «The Story of a Wise Old Man», «The Cloud in Love», «The Fox», «The Fox and Baba Ega», «A Thorn in the Crow's Fingers», «The Fox and the Fox», «Weavers», «The Tiger and the Cat», «The Underground Eagle», «The Venerable One», «The Old Woman and the Fox», «The Blind Tsar».

In the 1960-80s, the translation and publication of stories by writers Sabohatdin Ali and Aziz Nesin continued. Four stories by S. Ali were published in the newspapers «Soviet Tajikistan», «Kurgan-Tyube Pravda», «Obrazovanie i Kultura». The same newspapers published stories by Abboszade Hussein, Akcham Dursun, Rashot Nuri Guntekin, Suod Dervesh translated by Tajik translators U. Obidov, U. Kholikov, A. Amirjanov, F. Chariyev, K. Vasiyev. In the same years, more than thirty stories by Aziz Nesin were published in two collections, translated by R. Hashim from the original (a total of three stories) and Urun Kuhzad, Juma Odinaev from Russian. Familiarization with Turkish literature was also facilitated by the publication of studies and monographs on Turkish writers. In 1978, the Irfon publishing house released A. Nesin's novel «The King of Football». The newspaper «Komsomolets Tajikistan» No. 2 of 1960 published a translation of stories and novellas by Turkish writers. In the same publication, U. Kuhzod published an article about Nesin as a world-famous writer [1, 60].

Unfortunately, the insufficient number of studies in the field of the history of translation activities does not allow us to clarify the question of how the works of Turkish literature were perceived and assessed by the Tajik audience. And yet, the number of published works allows us to say that in the 60s and 80s of the 20th century, Tajikistan saw an increased interest in Turkish literature, which was facilitated by the development of good-neighborly relations between Tajikistan and Turkey, as well as the expansion of the circle of progressively minded literary intelligentsia. However, the question naturally arises as to how systematized, planned and high-quality the translation activity was. Despite the fact that many publishing houses issued translated series of novels of world literature, a considerable part of which belonged to Turkish writers, it should be noted that the choice for translation and subsequent publication of works of this or that author in these years still remained with the translators and publishers. In addition, most translations of works of Turkish literature in the years of language were carried out from books already translated into Western languages, i.e. through the intermediary language. Adaptations of texts and liberties of translation were allowed. It is clear that under such conditions it was not easy to evaluate the adequacy and quality of the translation. Based on all this, an urgent need for streamlining literary translation and publishing activities on the part of the state was clearly brewing.

A new stage in the history of Tajik-Turkish literary relations began in the second half of the 1960s. The growth of revolutionary sentiments among the youth and democratic intelligentsia was accompanied by an increase in interest in Turkish writers, the history and culture of the Turkish people. In the 1970s, there was a mass passion for Tajik and Turkish literature, in the full sense of the word. Works of Turkish prose of the 20th century, as well as books by Sabohatdin Ali, Guntekin Reshad Nuri, Nazim Hikmet, Aziz Nesin, Akcam Dursun, Suad Darvesh, Bakir

Yulduz, Fahri Erdinch, Hussein Abbaszade and others were republished in old and new translations or published for the first time [2, 23].

The consistent publication of translations of these works in the Tajik language attracted more and more attention from society to Turkish literature: newspapers increasingly published articles by writers and literary scholars with an analysis of translations and an assessment of the phenomenon of Turkish classics. However, despite the involvement of translation, and above all, artistic translation, in complex socio-political processes, it was still perceived by Tajik society as an aesthetic phenomenon designed to implement cultural contacts between countries, and thereby enable Tajikistan to take its special place in the world cultural space. Rahim Hashim, who translated the novel «The Songbird» (Gyuntekin R.N., published for the second time in 1984), became known as a translator of all the works of the storyteller of Turkish writers. He also introduced the Tajik readership to more than thirty works.

Thus, thanks to the work of translators, Tajik readers have the opportunity to read some works of Turkish literature in their native language. Many humorous works, for example, Nesin's short stories, have several versions of Tajik translation and are published by all metropolitan and provincial publishing houses. The review we have presented allows us not only to recreate in the most complete form the chronology of activities on the translation of works of Turkish literature in Tajikistan, but also to pay tribute to the true devotees of translation and publishing activities, who have made an invaluable contribution to the culture of Tajik society.

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